

TABLE 1

Sr. No.	Complex	% Co(II)	Analysis % N	Mol. wt.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (nm)
1.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ · 2H ₂ O]	22.29 (22.14)	10.32(10.68)	—	4.45	—
2.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ endn]	20.12 (20.05)	19.32(19.50)	304 (287)	4.69	430 (E = 14.64), 560, 835
3.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ pndn]	19.28 (19.40)	09.59(09.30)	309 (302)	4.70	435 (E = 17.22), 560, 740

Calculated values are in parantheses.

TABLE 2—(INFRA RED ASSIGNMENTS)

	endn	pndn	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ endn]	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ pndn]
N-H Stretch	3505 msp	3495 mbr	3440 mbr	3375 sbr
N-H bending	1655 msp	1650 msp	1635 mbr	1625 wbr
C-N Stretch	1225 ssp	1215 msp	1155 msp	1140 ssp
C = O Stretch	—	—	1590 mbr	1625 mbr

Abbreviation : endn = ethylenediamine, pndn = propylenediamine, pyr = 2-pyrrolidone, m = medium, s = strong, sp = sharp, br = broad.

frequency remains unaltered on coordination ; on the other hand the N-H bending vibration which usually occurs in the range 1500–1590 cm⁻¹ disappears on coordination, indicating that the coordination take place through nitrogen atom only.

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Flavonoid Constituents of *Lycopersicon esculentum*

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LYCOSPERSICON *esculentum* belongs to the family Solanaceae and is rich in vitamins A and C¹.

The defatted seeds of *L. esculentum* were first extracted with acidulated (1 N HCl) methanol and the study of the methanolic extract containing anthocyanins has already been communicated. Thereafter the seeds were extracted with cold acetone. The acetone extract after concentration under reduced pressure was treated with ether and the ethereal extract on concentration yielded a yellow solid mass which on paper chromatography and TLC

examination showed the presence of two ferric positive spots. The yellow solid mass was chromatographed on a column of silica gel and eluted with benzene : ethylacetate [(i) (75 : 25, V/V), (ii) (15 : 85, V/V)]. The eluate (i) gave compound X and eluate (ii) gave compound Y respectively.

Compound X was crystallised from a mixture of acetone : methanol (1 : 1), when light yellow crystals, m.p. 316°, C, 59.58; H, 3.33%, m/e = 302, molecular formula C₁₅H₁₀O₇, acetyl derivative, m.p. 198°–99°, were obtained. Co-chromatographic examination and mixed m.p. determination with authentic sample of quercetin confirmed it to be quercetin.

Compound Y crystallised from methanol (m.p. 274°–75°), responded to usual colour tests for flavonoids. It gave no positive Molisch's test indicating it to be a free flavone and not a glycoside. It was identified as Kaempferol by co-chromatography, mixed m.p. determination and superimposable spectral studies.

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A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part XXI. Cu(II) and Hg(II) Chelates of N-Benzenesulphonyl L(–) Aspartic Acid and N-Benzenesulphonyl L(+) Glutamic Acid

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IN a previous communication¹, complex compounds formed by the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl L(–) aspartic acid (R₂H₂) have been reported. Now a

comparative study has been made between $R_b^A H_3$ and N-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid ($R_b^G H_3$) on the basis of their acid dissociations and acid associations of their Hg(II) and Cu(II) complex ions, viz., $Cu(R_b^A)_2^{4-}$, $Hg(R_b^A)_2^{4-}$, $Cu(R_b^G)_2^{4-}$ and $Hg(R_b^G)_2^{4-}$.

Both $R_b^A H_3$ and $R_b^G H_3$ behave as weak dibasic acids in aqueous solution. Their successive acid dissociation constants have been determined potentiometrically at $31^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$). Acid association constants of the complex ions ($Cu(R_b^A)_2^{4-}$, $Hg(R_b^A)_2^{4-}$, $Cu(R_b^G)_2^{4-}$ and $Hg(R_b^G)_2^{4-}$) have been determined by potentiometric titration of their aqueous solutions with a standard solution of $HClO_4$ under identical conditions. Only two steps of their acid association could be followed as precipitation and/or decomposition set in on further titration. The constants have been evaluated graphically².

Experimental

Materials

(a) Ligands $R_b^A H_3$ and $R_b^G H_3$ were prepared by following the usual procedure described in the literature³ and dried at 105° .

(b) Complex compounds $Na_4Cu(R_b^A)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $Na_4Hg(R_b^A)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were prepared by following the methods reported in our previous communication¹. $Na_4Cu(R_b^G)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $Na_4Hg(R_b^G)_2$ were also prepared following the similar procedure. All the complexes were dried to constant weight in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and KOH as they were hygroscopic. Their molecular compositions were determined by estimating Na and Cu or Hg. All other reagents were either of A.R. quality or properly purified and their solutions were made in double distilled CO_2 free water.

Apparatus :

Measurements of pH values were made with a Cambridge portable type pH meter using glass electrode of 1-13 pH range in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar-2M $NaNO_3$ bridge.

Procedure :

Experimental procedure consists of potentiometric titrations of 50 ml ligand solutions (0.01M or 0.0075M) containing known amount of free $HClO_4$ with 0.07681M NaOH solution and 50 ml complex ion solutions (0.01M or 0.0075M) with 0.1M $HClO_4$ at $31^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Ionic strength was maintained constant ($\mu = 0.5$) throughout by adding requisite amount of

$NaClO_4$. Equilibrium concentrations of H^+ and OH^- were evaluated by graphical method⁴.

Results

Acid dissociation constants (k_3^* and k_2^*) of the ligands $R_b^A H_3$ and $R_b^G H_3$:

The three steps of acid dissociation of the ligand $R_b^A H_3$ or $R_b^G H_3$ may be represented as

where RH_3 is $R_b^A H_3$ or $R_b^G H_3$ and the successive acid dissociation constants are given by (4), (5) and (6)

$$k_3^* = \frac{[RH_2^-][H^+]}{[RH_3]} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$k_2^* = \frac{[RH^-][H^+]}{[RH_2^-]} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$k_1^* = \frac{[R^{3-}][H^+]}{[RH^-]} \quad \dots (6)$$

Now, at any stage of the titration after the attainment of equilibrium the relation

$$R = R_3 + R_2 + R_1 + R_0 \quad \dots (7)$$

holds good, where R is initial concentration of RH_3 ; R_3 , R_2 , R_1 and R_0 are the equilibrium concentrations of RH_3 , RH_2^- , RH^- and R^{3-} respectively. As the solution is electroneutral

$$P + H^+ = F + OH^- + R_2 + 2R_1 + 3R_0 \quad \dots (8)$$

where F and P are the initial concentrations and H^+ and OH^- are the equilibrium concentrations of acid and alkali respectively.

The average number ($\bar{n}_H$) of protons bound to the ligand ion R^{3-} is given by

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{3R_3 + 2R_2 + R_1}{R_3 + R_2 + R_1 + R_0} \quad \dots (9)$$

and then from (7), (8) and (9) one may get

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{1}{R} (3R - P + F - H^+ + OH^-) \quad \dots (10)$$

The acid dissociation curves (Figs. 1 and 2) were obtained on plotting $\bar{n}_H$ against pH. As indicated by $\bar{n}_H$ values upto $pH \approx 9.5$, the dissociation represented by (3) would not take place. Therefore presence of R^{3-} in solution was neglected. Due to overlapping of the steps represented by (1) and (2), k_3^* and k_2^* values were evaluated from linear plots of the relation (11)

$$\left(\frac{3 - \bar{n}_H}{\bar{n}_H - 1} \right) [H^+]^2 = -k_3^* \left(\frac{2 - \bar{n}_H}{\bar{n}_H - 1} \right) [H^+] + k_3^* k_2^* \quad (11)$$

which may be deduced from equations (4), (5) and (9). Results are stated in Table 1. The $\bar{n}_H$ values

have been calculated using the experimentally determined values of k_3^* and k_2^* employing the relation

$$\bar{n}_{H(\text{calc.})} = \frac{3[\text{H}^+]^2 + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} + 1}{\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_3^* k_2^*} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} + 1} \quad \dots (12)$$

Fig. 1. Acid dissociation curve of Rb_4H_3 and acid association curves of its $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complex ions. Rb_4H_3 0.01M $\square$; 0.0075M $\blacktriangle$; calculated curve employing $\text{pk}_3^* = 2.84$ and $\text{pk}_2^* = 4.41$, —. $\text{Cu}(\text{Rb}_4)_2^{4-}$ 9.10M Δ ; 0.0075M $\blacksquare$; calculated curve employing $\log K_1 = 7.60$ and $\log K_2 = 4.83$, - - - - - $\text{Hg}(\text{Rb}_4)_2^{4-}$ 0.01 M $\circ$; 0.0075M $\bullet$; calculated curve employing $\log K_1 = 5.28$ and $\log K_2 = 4.36$, - - - - -.

Fig. 2. Acid dissociation curve of Rb_6H_3 and acid association curves of its $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complex ions. Rb_6H_3 0.01 M $\circ$; 0.0075M $\bullet$; calculated curve employing $\text{pk}_3^* = 2.99$ and $\text{pk}_2^* = 4.53$, —. $\text{Cu}(\text{Rb}_6)_2^{4-}$ 0.01 M $\square$; 0.0075 M $\blacktriangle$; calculated curve employing $\log K_1 = 7.11$ and $\log K_2 = 5.30$, - - - - - $\text{Hg}(\text{Rb}_6)_2^{4-}$ 0.01M Δ ; 0.0075M $\blacksquare$; calculated curve employing $\log K_1 = 5.30$ and $\log K_1 = 4.62$, - - - - -.

and calculated acid dissociation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_{H(\text{calc.})}$ against pH (Figs. 1 and 2)

TABLE I—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND ACID ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THEIR $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ AND $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ COMPLEX IONS

Species	pk_3^*	pk_2^*	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$
Rb_4H_3	2.84	4.41		
Rb_6H_3	2.99	4.53		
$\text{Cu}(\text{Rb}_4)_2^{4-}$			4.83	7.60
$\text{Hg}(\text{Rb}_4)_2^{4-}$			4.36	5.28
$\text{Cu}(\text{Rb}_6)_2^{4-}$			5.30	7.11
$\text{Hg}(\text{Rb}_6)_2^{4-}$			4.62	5.30

Acid association constants (K_1 and K_2 of the $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complex ions) :

Two acid association steps for the complex ions may be represented as

where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ and $\text{RH}_3 = \text{Rb}_4\text{H}_3$ or Rb_6H_3 , for which the successive acid association constants (K_1 and K_2) are given by equation (13) and (14) respectively.

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{M}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^{3-}]}{[\text{M}(\text{R})_2^{4-}][\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (15)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{M}(\text{RH})_2^{2-}]}{[\text{M}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^{3-}][\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (16)$$

Now at any stage of the titration after attainment of equilibrium the relations

$$\text{M} = \text{M}_0 + \text{M}_1 + \text{M}_2 \quad \dots (17)$$

and as the solution is electroneutral

$$4\text{M} + \text{H}^+ = 4\text{M}_0 + 3\text{M}_1 + 2\text{M}_2 + \text{OH}^- + \text{F} \quad \dots (18)$$

hold good where M is the initial concentration of $\text{M}(\text{R})_2^{4-}$ ions, M_0 , M_1 and M_2 are the equilibrium concentrations of complex ions $\text{M}(\text{R})_2^{4-}$, $\text{M}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^{3-}$, $\text{M}(\text{RH})_2^{2-}$ respectively. Other rotations have their usual meanings.

The average number of protons ($\bar{n}_h$) bound to the complex $\text{M}(\text{R})_2^{4-}$ ion is given by

$$\bar{n}_h = \frac{\text{M}_1 + 2\text{M}_2}{\text{M}_0 + \text{M}_1 + \text{M}_2} \quad \dots (19)$$

and from (17), (18) and (19) one may get

$$\bar{n}_h = \frac{1}{\text{M}}(\text{F} - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}^-) \quad \dots (20)$$

The K_1 and K_2 values have been evaluated from linear plots of the relation

$$\left(\frac{2-\bar{n}_h}{\bar{n}_h}\right)[H^+]^2 = -\frac{1}{K_2}\left(\frac{1-\bar{n}_h}{\bar{n}_h}\right)[H^+] + \frac{1}{K_1K_2} \quad \dots (21)$$

deduced from equations (15), (16) and (19). Results are stated in Table 1.

The $\bar{n}_h$ values have also been calculated using the experimentally determined values of K_1 and K_2 employing the relation

$$\bar{n}_h(\text{calc.}) = \frac{2K_1K_2[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+]}{K_1K_2[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + 1} \quad \dots (22)$$

and calculated acid association curves [$\bar{n}_h(\text{calc.})$ against pH] were drawn along with the experimental points (Figs. 1 and 2).

Discussion

As expected $R_6^4H_3$ has been found to be stronger acid than $R_6^6H_3$ indicated by pK^* values (Table 1) evidently due to the interpolation of one more methylene group in between two $-COOH$ groups in $R_6^6H_3$.

Proton dissociation constants of complex compounds such as $-SO_2HN : \rightarrow M \leftarrow : NHO_2S-$ are related to the metal ligand stability constants. The stronger is the $M-N$ bond, the more easily dissociable is the proton bound to nitrogen. Acid association constants of the complex ions are therefore taken as a measure of instability of the complexes⁴, the stability order is $Hg(II) > Cu(II)$. The deviation of the experimental points from the calculated curves (Figs. 1 and 2) at the later stages of titrations i.e., at lower pH values, is due to the commencement of precipitation and/or decomposition of the complex compounds. For $Hg(II)$ complexes, the more basic is the ligand, the easier is the protonation of the complex ion. But regarding $Cu(II)$ complexes, no definite conclusion could be made as the protonation of the complex ion $Cu(R_6^6)_2^{4-}$ appears to be a complex one indicated by appreciable deviation of the experimental points from the calculated curve (Fig. 2) also at the earlier stages of titrations. Similar results have also been obtained for $Cu(R_6^6)_2^{4-}$ where titrations were made with HNO_3 using KNO_3 as the background electrolyte⁵.

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Potential Antidiabetics: Bis-Benzimidazole-2-Sulphonamido Derivatives

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SYNTHALIN¹ is known as a compound with high hypoglycemic activity. The length of the carbon chain in the molecule which is $-(CH_2)_{10}-$ may be one of the factors which is responsible for such an activity². Carbutamide and tolbutamide also possess a marked hypoglycemic action which may be due to the sulphonamido group which each contains³. Urea 1,1'-ethylene bis-3-(*p*-tolylsulphonyl) and its analogues were tested for their hypoglycemic activity and was found that they lowered the blood sugar level when given orally⁴.

Okamoto and co-workers⁵ have reported that benzimidazole nucleus itself has high antidiabetic activity. An examination of the above facts together with the encouraging results we have obtained from benzimidazole derivatives⁶ with sulphonamido group substituted at position 2 of the benzimidazole nucleus prompted us to synthesise a new series of compounds represented by I containing benzimidazole nucleus, sulphonamido group and a varying long chain carbon linkage not examined so far for their antidiabetic property. It was thought that this would probably lead to compounds possessing greater antidiabetic activity.

I

Experimental

Preparation of 2-benzimidazolesulphonyl chloride⁸:

2-mercapto benzimidazole⁷ 20 g in 800 ml of 20% ACOH was cooled in an ice bath and Cl_2 was passed first slowly and then vigorously for 50-55 min. The product was filtered quickly.

General method for the preparation of bis-benzimidazole-2-sulphonamide derivatives:

A mixture of 2 moles of the above sulphonyl chloride and 1 mole of the diamines in 20 ml of dry pyridine was refluxed for 3-4 hrs. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was washed with cold water and then recrystallised from water to give the compounds mentioned in Table 1.

Pharmacology:

The compounds were studied for their hypoglycemic action in albino rats of either sex weighing

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